

THE MANUFACTURING OF AL/AL₂O₃ COMPOSITES BY SPRAYING-OXIDATION PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The Al/Al₂O₃ composites are produced by a method called spraying-oxidation process. The alumina is formed through the oxidation reaction of molten aluminium and is dispersed in the Al matrix. The structure of the composite is examined and the effects of processing factors on the formation of Al₂O₃ particles, their quantity and size distribution are investigated. Also the mechanical properties of the composite are tested.

Keywords: composite, Al/Al₂O₃, spraying-oxidation

1. INTRODUCTION

The research and development of metal matrix composites has been one of the most active area in materials science and technology for past decades. A Metal Matrix Composites Information Analysis Center (MMCIAC) has been established in United State of American to promote the study and application of metal matrix composites. In Europe, Japan and other countries, great attentions have been taken to this field and significant progress has been achieved. In facts, some continuous fiboure reinforced metal matrix composites have been used successfully in the aerospace and automobile industries.[1-6]

The continuous fiboure reinforced metal matrix composites, compared to the conventional engineering materials, provide much more excellent properties, but the complicate processing technology and high cost limites their application to the industries. In recent years, more and more interests have been paid to the particle or whisker reinforced metal matrix composites, because these composites can be produced by powder metallurgy or casting process. However, there are considerable problems involved in the introduction of second phase to the metal, such as the dispersion of particles which are not wetted by the liquid metal, the segregation during solidification or interface reaction between the reinforcement phase and the molten matrix metal.

The new spraying-oxidation process was developed to produce Al/Al₂O₃ composites, in which the Al₂O₃ is formed by the direct oxidation of Al melt. In this method, the problems involved the introducing of the reinforced phase to the matrix metal are overcome.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Principle of Oxidation

Under the condition of oxidizing atmosphere, Al melt will be oxidized immediately, according to

the following formula.

The formed Al_2O_3 on the surface of pure Al melt has a dense structure and high hardness.

The oxidation rate is directly related to the temperature of Al, as shown in Figure 1. It increases gradually with the increase of temperature. As the temperature close to the melting point of Al, the oxidation rate increases greatly. Once the formation of Al_2O_3 layer the oxidation process is controlled by the atom diffusion process and the rate is reduced.

Figure 1. illustration of the oxidation rate of Al at different temperature[7]

Another important factor influencing the oxidation of Al is the surface area of Al exposed to the oxidizing atmosphere. The larger this exposed area is, the greater the degree of oxidation. In the spraying-oxidation process the Al melt is atomized into a lot of liquid droplets, producing a much greater surface exposing to the oxidizing atmosphere. Al_2O_3 is formed at the surface of these droplets and, then, the mixture of Al and Al_2O_3 is deposited together on a substrate. The Al_2O_3 layer at the surface of the Al droplets is broken into a number of particles which are dispersed in the rapidly solidified Al matrix. The total process is finished within a very short time and it can be performed continuously. Also the degree of oxidation and the quantity of Al_2O_3 formed can be controlled by adjusting the temperature, the oxidizing atmosphere, or the atomization process.

2.2. Experimental Condition

The test materials used in this investigation is pure foundry Al ingots, no alloying elements are added. The Al is melted in an electrical resistance furnace and the melting temperature is about 800°C . The melt, after removing the flooding inclusions, is poured into an atomization chamber. The oxidizing medium is a gas mixture of O_2 and N_2 . With the total gas pressure constant, the O_2 content in the oxidizing medium is adjusted by changing the partial pressure of O_2 or N_2 .

The effects of pouring temperature and the gas pressure on the formation of Al_2O_3 are tested under the condition of other factors unchanged.

Microstructure observation and mechanical properties tests are performed on the samples of Al/ Al_2O_3 composite obtained.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Microstructure Observation

Figure 2 shows the typical microstructure of Al/ Al_2O_3 composite produced by the spraying-oxidation process. The X-ray diffraction analysis indicates that the white particles in Figure 2 are Al_2O_3 .

The results of X-ray diffraction analysis are listed in Table 1, the 2θ values are measured

from the diffraction peaks in the recorded diffraction curves (the diffraction peaks for pure Al are not included). The corresponding d values are calculated by using the Bragg Law. These d values are exactly same as the diffraction data found from the Box 10-425 of 1980 diffraction cards, which belong to the Al₂O₃ materials. Therefore, it can be determined that, except for Al, only Al₂O₃ exists in these samples.

Figure 2 microstructure of Al/Al₂O₃ composite by spraying-oxidation process

Table 1. results of X-ray diffraction

2 θ	29.4	45.6	66.3	79.1	83.4
d (calculated)	2.2869	1.9893	1.4159	1.2107	1.159
d (date)	2.28	1.98	1.41	1.21	1.15

The EDAX analysis on the matrix and the white particles also shows the present of element Al only.

A number of SEM observations are performed on the composites produced under different processing condition. The results indicate that the Al₂O₃ particles are dispersed randomly in the matrix, with an irregular form and fine size of less than 10 μm. Some of the larger particles consist of several small particles clustered together. In addition, a small amount of microporosity is present in the as-deposited matrix, which can be reduced effectively but can not be eliminated completely by adjusting processing parameters.

3.2 Al₂O₃ Quantity and Size Distribution

Samples obtained under different processing condition are examined with SEM. At least three photos are taken from different view field for each sample, on which the average size and percentage content of Al₂O₃ particles are measured. These results are shown in Figure 3 to Figure 5. It can be concluded that with higher oxygen content in the oxidizing medium, more Al₂O₃ are produced. By increasing the total gas pressure, the size of Al₂O₃ particle decreases and the quantity keeps constant. With higher pouring temperature, the size of Al₂O₃ particle is also reduced but the quantity increases slightly.

Figure 3. effect of oxygen content on Al₂O₃ fraction

Figure 4. effect of total pressure on Al₂O₃ fraction and size distribution

Figure 5. effect of pouring temperature on Al₂O₃ fraction and size distribution

3.3. Mechanical Properties

Limited tests are performed on the composite samples to measure the tensile strength and hardness. The configuration and dimension of the tensile sample is shown in Figure 6. The processing parameters for the tested samples are: total gas pressure 0.9 MPa, oxygen content in the oxidizing medium is 20%, pouring temperature is 750°C. For compare, samples of metal Al are also made.

Figure 6. illustration of the tensile sample

The results are listed in Table 2, compared to the Al matrix, the composite by spraying-oxidation process provides a much higher tensile strength and hardness. However, the strength value only reaches to 174 MPa, the reasons for this low strength level may be considered as 1) the low strength of matrix metal itself. Since the Al₂O₃ particles of 10-15% is dispersed in the matrix, the tensile load is supported mainly by the matrix metal. So the strength of the composite can be increased by increasing the strength of the matrix metal; 2) the presence of microporosity in the as-deposited composite, which reduces the strength, and this may be improved by forming, rolling or extrusion processes.

Table 2. the strength and hardness of the samples

material	condition	σ_b , MPa	δ , %	HB
Al	as cast	92.0	22	31
		99.1	19	28
Al/Al ₂ O ₃	as deposited	162.0	18	47
		174.0	11	44

note: Each date is the average value of three samples.

3.4. Discussion on Al/Al₂O₃ Interface

In this type of composite there are two types of possible interface structure at the Al/Al₂O₃ interface. One is the contineous structure from Al₂O₃ to Al which is formed by the surface Al₂O₃ layer and the unoxidized metal Al. Another is formed during the deposition, that is, the broken Al₂O₃ particles surrounded by the unoxidized and rapidly solidified Al melt. The TEM observation [8] shows that a strong connection between the Al₂O₃ particle and the matrix metal has been obtained and no obvious transition layer is observed at the interface. It can be concluded that at temperature over the melting point of Al the fresh surfaces of Al₂O₃ and Al melt is clean and active, resulting a good connection between Al₂O₃ and Al melt.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the above investigation, the following conclusions can be obtained.

1) With the spraying-oxidation process, Al melt is atomized and oxidized simultaneously. Al₂O₃ is formed at the surface of liquid troplets of Al and, after deposition and solidification, Al/Al₂O₃ composite is obtained.

2) The Al₂O₃ particles in the composite appears as different shapes, distributed randomly in the Al matrix. Their sizes are less than 10 um. By adjusting the concentration of oxidizing medium or processing parameters, the quantity of Al₂O₃ particles and their size distribution can be easily adjusted.

3) Compared to the Al matrix, the composite provides a much higher tensile strength and hardness. The Al₂O₃ particles formed by the spraying-oxidation method indicates a significantly strengthening ability.

4) In this composite a good interface connection can be obtained between Al₂O₃ and Al matrix. Further works will include the optimization of the composition of matrix alloy, and combining the spraying-oxidation method with the forming or rolling process to eliminate the microporosity in the composite. It can be expected that this new composite will have high strength, good wear resistance and heat resistance. In addition, the low processing cost will provide a promising future of application for this composite to the industries.

Acknowledgements

This research is supported by the State Education Committee and the 863 project. The contributors to this work also include Y.L. Li, J.H. Zhao, X.M. Zhang.

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